

MECHANISMS AND PROSPECTS OF TRAINING PERSONNEL WITH SCIENTIFIC COMPETENCE IN THE FIELD OF PSYCHOLOGY

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Anotation : Training of personnel with scientific potential in the field of psychology remains one of the main tasks today. It is today that it is described about the training of personnel with scientific potential and the creation of conditions for them and the development of its various methods ,paths ,giving instructions.

Аннотация: Подготовка кадров, обладающих научным потенциалом в области психологии, остается сегодня одним из главных вопросов. Сегодня говорится о подготовке кадров, обладающих научным потенциалом, и создании для них условий, а также разработке различных методов, способов и инструкций.

Keywords: Psychology , capacity frame , psychological mechanism , modern trends, psychological service .

Ключевые слова: Психология, потенциальный персонал, психологический механизм, современные тенденции, психологическая служба.

In recent years, a number of activities related to the training of pedagogic personnel in the field of psychology and supporting the activities of practicing psychologists have been carried out in the country. Today, the training of qualified personnel in modern psychology and the expansion of the scope of higher educational institutions in the fields of psychology are being carried out. Measures and measures to increase the psychological literacy of the population were considered and implemented.

Despite the scale of the work, there are still a number of problems that need to be solved immediately.

firstly, although there are psychological personnel and organizations specializing in the diagnosis of the psychological condition of young people at all levels of the educational system, the lack of a single structure to coordinate and manage their activities affects the low level of effectiveness of psychological services;

- secondly, although preventive inspectors and community representatives' offices have been established in educational institutions, the directions of their cooperation with educational institutions and the mechanisms for evaluating the effectiveness of their activities have not been determined;
- thirdly, as a result of insufficient provision of psychological services to the population, socio-psychological, including family problems (divorces, family disputes, parent-child relations, marriage between relatives, early childbirth), subject to the negative effects of "mass culture", cases of suicide continue;
- fourthly, the knowledge of practicing psychologists trained in the field of psychology in the higher education system remains general, and the practice of training specialists in a narrow field has not been established;
- fifthly, due to the low number of admissions to master's and doctoral degrees in the field of psychology, there is a weakness in the formation of the national school of psychology;
- sixthly, the financial incentives of psychologists, the unsatisfactory state of activity of centers providing psychological services to the population do not give them the opportunity to attract experienced psychologists. It is not an exaggeration to say that, in order to provide convenient quality psychological services to the population in our republic, sufficient attention and recognition is being paid to the field of psychology and to the provision of psychological services to the population. A psychologist is the creator and shaper of the human heart. At this point, it is permissible to provide information about psychological services. The main content of psychological services is to ensure the growth of a healthy person, to correct various difficulties in personal development, and the problems of choosing a profession. The main tasks of a psychological consultant in Czechoslovakia function consists of psychodiagnostic activity. In former Soviet psychology, attempts to use psychology in children's upbringing and education were made within the framework of pedology.

The initial roots and end of the formation of the psychological service in Uzbekistan go back to the activities of the pedological science and pedological service in the 30s of our century. In these years, the organization and development of the educational process is based on psychological factors related to the activity of the

student and the teacher, and only this has given good results. However, unfortunately, a stream of some objective and subjective conflicts that arose between the ideology of the former union and public education at that time struck the root of the pedagogical service, which was of great importance for general education schools, and officially took out. As a result, all work carried out by pedagogical psychology was carried out in school only on the basis of pedagogical approaches. Nevertheless, researches and studies related to the general education system in Uzbekistan have not stopped. Especially P. I. Ivanov, V. E. Chudnovsky, M.G. A number of scientific and methodical recommendations developed by Davletshin, M. Vohidov served as a basis for the implementation of psychological services at school.

In conclusion, it can be said that today's field of psychology and providing psychological services in it is performed in theory and practice. The role of psychology in the educational system and its effectiveness are becoming known. Development and progress will continue in a country with a mentally and physically mature person. For this purpose, improving the quality of education and training qualified personnel are among the urgent problems of today's education policy. If our education is of high quality, systematic, and continuous, and if we approach it based on world experience, we would find ways to solve these problems, at least a little. and effective results will be reflected.

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